

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF RESIN INFILTRATION PROCESS ON 3D FIBROUS REINFORCEMENT AT MULTISCALE

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ABSTRACT

This work presents the resin infiltration process during VARTM (Vacuum Assisted Resin Transfer Molding) process on 3D fibrous model at multi-scale by adopting numerical simulation to estimate the permeability and to track the transient resin flow front by level set method. The transient saturation during infiltration process is studied by introducing infiltration ratio. Influence of structural parameters of the fibrous media, inlet pressure and resin property on the infiltration process is also discussed.

1 INTRODUCTION

VARTM process is one of the most significant process of LCM (Liquid Composite Molding). Compared with other processes, VARTM has numerous advantages such like good surface quality, low-cost and high efficiency. Resin infiltration is the mean step of this process. Nowadays, the numerical simulation of the resin infiltration in the 3D fibrous reinforcement at multiscale mostly focus on the permeability estimation. This work is interested in using FEM (Finite element method) to study the transient flow front tracking based on 3D REV (representative elementary volume) model including both woven and unidirectional fibrous structure at multiscale. However, in the practical process of VARTM, both the flow outside tows and infusion intra tow include complex hydromechanics procedure, micro and macro voids formation greatly depend on transient situation.

For VARTM process, there is only one phase (resin) flow. In the region of inter tows, Navier-Stokes equation can be applied to simulate the free surface flow while Brinkman equation governs the flow intra tows. This single-phase method is suitable to describe the present challenges, since Brinkman equation has been employed only to solve single-phase coupling problem so far and it is indicated that this equation will cause numerous problems in two-phase porous flow. Level set method is implemented to track the resin flow front.

Permeability is the most crucial parameter of porous structural media. It is an intrinsic property of the fibrous reinforcement and the value of it will influence the infusion situation to great extent. Obviously, the structure of the porous media has direct influence on the permeability. Permeability estimation at meso-scale is a hot and important topic. Geometrical model setup is the basic step of numerical simulation, since different architectures will form special computation domains and lead to variant flow stratagems. At micro scale, Chen et al. [1] has explored the influence of the fiber structure inside a tow. At meso-scale level, since the limitation of the computation devices and time cost, unit cell models are essential and widely implemented in Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). According to literature reviews, various modelling strategies have been developed to describe the complex fibrous structure at meso-scale. Nordlund and Lundstrom [2] explored the permeability of NCFs (Noncrimp stitched Fabrics) structure Zeng X. et al. [3] applied software Texgen to produce woven fabric structures, Hai L. L. and Wook R. H. [4] set up the plain woven fiber tow model with shear rate distribution. Potluri P. and Sagar TV. [5] applied an energy minimisation scheme to deal with modelling the compaction behaviour of dry fibre assemblies. In this research, a trigonometric function is adopted as the central curve of the woven fibrous tow while the sections along the central

curve path are set as uniform ellipse.

2 GEOMETRICAL MODEL DEFINITION

Geometrical model is the basis of a numerical simulation process. The modelling structure will have direct influence on the computation results. According to the research of Potluri P. and Sagar TV. [5], during the first stage of compression, as shown in figure 1 and figure 2a, the relation between pressure and thickness is linear and there is distance δ between the fiber tows in vertical direction, which means fiber tows are not contact with each other. In the practical numerical simulation, for the geometrical fiber model, the intersections between fiber tows will cause the loss in tow volume, and then affect the numerical inaccuracy in predicting fiber tow permeability by CFD method [6]. In this research, even in highly packed cases, a thin gap between tows is reserved to avoid numerical inaccuracy. Hence, the change of the section shape of the fiber tows (figure 2) is not considered.

Figure 1: Typical compression curve of a woven fabric

Figure 2: Stages of fabric compression

The middle of the woven fibrous tow is defined by the curve related to the trigonometric function of equation 1:

$$y = \frac{\alpha \cdot x_{max} \cdot \sin x}{10} \quad (1)$$

Where y is the amplitude of the curve, x is the axial coordinate in x direction ($x \geq 0$). α is defined as the modulation parameter of the waviness of the fiber tow.

In Figure 3, the influence of the α value on the variation of the position of the middle of the woven fibrous tow is represented with a length of a wave period to 10 mm. α value varies from 1 to 1/2 in five levels ($\alpha = 1, 4/5, 2/3, 4/7, 1/2$).

Figure 3: Influence of the parameter α on the variation of the tow central path

It is seen that, the waviness reduced accordingly with the decrease of the value α . When $\alpha = 1$, it can be considered as the initial situation of a fiber tow, while α turns to be 1/2, it can be deemed to that under the compression condition of the fiber tow. Herein, the compression and variation status of the fiber tows are directly expressed by the definition of the geometrical models.

Figure 4: Model setup of woven fibrous unit cell

The sections along the central curve path are defined as ellipse as shown in figure 4. a and b are the semi-major axis and semi-minor axis respectively. w is the width of the unit square cell, while h is the height of the unit cell. The 3D unidirectional fibrous model is set up as presented in figure 5.

Figure 5: 3D unidirectional fibrous unit cell

3 MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

3.1 Formulation of free flow and porous flow at dual scales

Stokes equation can be widely applied in all the free flow domain. For the flow inside the porous media, Brinkman equation is more suitable [7]. Classical single domain approach considers the physical properties at the interface of free flow and the porous flow transfer continuously. Hence, the flow both intra and inter porous media are continuous and can be described by an uniform Stokes-Brinkman equation [8] as shown in equations 2 and 3.

$$\mathbf{0} = \nabla \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)] - \frac{\mu}{\varepsilon}\mathbf{K}^{-1} + \mathbf{F} \quad (2)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0 \quad (3)$$

Where ρ , \mathbf{u} , p , μ , \mathbf{F} , \mathbf{I} , ε are density, velocity, pressure, viscosity, volume force, unit matrix and porosity of the fibrous tow respectively. In the porous flow media, the Darcy's term " $\frac{\mu}{\varepsilon}\mathbf{K}^{-1}$ " shows its function, while in the free flow domain, $\varepsilon = 1$ and \mathbf{K} verges on infinity, the Darcy's term can be ignored, and eq.6.1 can be simplified as Stokes equation.

3.2 Intra tow permeability definition

For the 3D model case, in a cartesian coordinate system, the permeability in three directions of the intra fibrous tow can be expressed as shown below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{xx} & K_{xy} & K_{xz} \\ K_{yx} & K_{yy} & K_{yz} \\ K_{zx} & K_{zy} & K_{zz} \end{bmatrix}$$

The yarn tows are set to be parallel to the x, y, z coordinates, thus, $K_{yx}=K_{xy} = 0$ and $K_{zx}=K_{xz} = 0$ and

K_{xx} , K_{yy} , K_{zz} are named as principle permeability while the meantime, x , y , z are the principle permeability directions as illustrated in

Figure 6 So K_1 permeability system is parallel to x, y direction; K_2 permeability system follows the central curve of the tow. K_{\perp}^1 and K_{\parallel}^1 are permeabilities in transverse and axial direction of K_1 permeability system, while K_{\perp}^2 and K_{\parallel}^2 are the similar definition of K_2 permeability system.

Figure 6: Principle permeability direction

Currently, some researches [9, 10] have performed the calculation of the permeability of unit cell by applying available CFD software or codes, and most of them used the permeability matrix listed above. The material properties such like permeability at micro scale can only be set as a universe value on the same domain by the software. Therefore, the influence of the variation with the geometrical domain on the material properties is hardly reflecting in the simulation results.

For the considered non-crimp fabric tows, we can suppose, in a first hypothesis that the principle permeability direction does not change along the fiber tow. In this situation, for the tows which are along with the inlet flow direction, the permeability of the fibrous tow should be defined as below:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{\parallel} & & \\ & K_{\perp} & \\ & & K_{\perp} \end{bmatrix}$$

While for the tows which are perpendicular to the inlet flow direction, the permeability of the tow can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{\perp} & & \\ & K_{\parallel} & \\ & & K_{\perp} \end{bmatrix}$$

For woven fiber cases, the direction of principle permeability K_{prin} varies with the waviness of the tow and the permeability should be projected to K' direction. At the meantime, for 3D woven fiber structure, only the 2D tensor coordinate transformation is required since the flow is in plane. According to the tensor methodology,

$$K_{prin} = \begin{bmatrix} K_{\parallel} & \\ & K_{\perp} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$K' = \begin{bmatrix} K_{11} & K_{12} \\ K_{21} & K_{22} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} K_{11} \\ K_{22} \\ K_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos^2\theta & \sin^2\theta & 2\cos\theta\sin\theta \\ \sin^2\theta & \cos^2\theta & -2\cos\theta\sin\theta \\ -\cos\theta\sin\theta & \cos\theta\sin\theta & \cos^2\theta - \sin^2\theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} K_{\parallel} \\ K_{\perp} \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Where $K_{12}=K_{21}$, θ is the angle between the principle permeability direction and the actual permeability direction as presented in Figure 6.

4 FLOW FRONT TRACKING: LEVEL SET METHOD (LSM)

Level Set Method is a common method implemented in interface tracking. Continuous function $\Phi(x,t)$ is introduced as the Level Set Method, by solving the controlling equation of the fluid domain, the position of the flow front interface $\Gamma_s(t)$ can be obtained. As depicted in Figure , the whole flow domain Ω includes fluid 1 (Ω_1) and fluid 2 (Ω_2), and the interface $\Gamma_s(t)$. In Level Set Method, we can define for Ω_1 domain, $0 < \Phi < 0.5$ while for Ω_2 , $0.5 < \Phi < 1$, $\Phi = 0.5$ represents the interface. Therefore, the level set function $\Phi(x,t)$ should obey the condition that $\Gamma_s(t)$ must be the zero contour $\Phi(x,t) = 0.5$ at any time. That means:

$$\Gamma_s(t) = \{x \in \Omega, \Omega = \Omega_1 \cup \Omega_2: \Phi(x,t) = 0.5\} \quad (4)$$

Generally, initial value $\Phi(x,t=0)$ represents t [11] from x to the interface $\Gamma_s(t=0)$, and the “signed distance” is a very typical sort of implicit equation:

$$\Phi(x,t=0) = \begin{cases} 0 \leq \text{dis}(x, \Gamma_s(t=0)) \leq 0.5, & x \in \Omega_1 \\ 0.5 & x \in \Gamma_s(t=0) \\ 0.5 \leq \text{dis}(x, \Gamma_s(t=0)) \leq 1, & x \in \Omega_2 \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where $\text{dis}(s, \Gamma_s(t=0))$ describes the distance from point x to interface $\Gamma_s(t=0)$ as shown in figure 7.

Figure 7: Fluid domain Ω_1 and Ω_2

Governing equation of level set function $\Phi(x,t)$ is given by (6):

$$\frac{\partial \Phi}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \Phi = \gamma \nabla \cdot \left(\epsilon \nabla \Phi - \Phi(1 - \Phi) \frac{\nabla \Phi}{|\nabla \Phi|} \right) \quad (6)$$

Where ϵ is the interface thickness controlling parameter while γ is the reinitialization parameter. A suitable value for γ is the maximum velocity magnitude occurring in the model. Here, for viscosity we applied an approximation value calculated by equation 8. In the multi-physics coupling feature, we define the density ρ (kg/m^3) and the μ viscosity ($\text{Pa}\cdot\text{s}$) as followings:

$$\rho = \rho_1 + (\rho_2 - \rho_1)\phi \quad (7)$$

$$\mu = \mu_1 + (\mu_2 - \mu_1)\phi \quad (8)$$

Where the value of ϕ varies from 0 to 1. By solving eq.2, eq.3 and level set equations together, flow front prediction can be obtained.

In fact, for the flow front tracking, the target is to solve the interface function $\Gamma_s(t)$ which depends on the propagation velocities on both Ω_1 and Ω_2 . In normal two-phase flow system research [12], the velocity field is obtained by solving Stokes equations of two phases flow, and the fluid properties vary smoothly on the thickness of the interface. Various methods are applied to carry on the one phase flow simulation, such as the method so called pseudo-fluid defining the incompressibility of fluid [13]. However there are all kinds of weak points as discussed in reference [14]. And in this study, the harmonically extended approach [15] is implemented as illustrated in equation 9.

$$\epsilon_r \nu + \epsilon_a \alpha_w \nabla^2 \nu = \epsilon_r \mu \quad (9)$$

Where ν is the velocity that will be applied to figure out parameter ϕ ; μ is the fluid velocity; when tuning factor α_w is a small constant value, $\epsilon_a = 1 - \epsilon_r$; and ϵ_r can be depicted as equation 10:

$$\epsilon_r = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_1 \\ 0 & \text{if } \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_2 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

5 BOUNDARY CONDITIONS AND INITIAL VALUES

For the simulation of the flow, pressure difference is set as the driving reason for flow between the front surface (S11) and the back surface (S22); periodic boundary conditions are set on the other four surfaces in two pairs (S33, S44 and S55, S66). The boundary conditions as illustrated in Figure 8.

(a) Intra tow domain

(b) Inter tow domain

(c) Boundary conditions
Figure 8: The whole model domain

6 FURTHER RESEARCH ON THE DUAL-SCALE MODELS

The transient flow front on different 3D models at meso-scale can be achieved as presented in figure 9. When pressure at the inlet is high enough, the resin flow is faster outside the tows than intra tows, since the pressure is the dominant influence for infusion process. While under relatively low pressure, the capillary force is the main reason for flow. Hence, the flow front intra tows is faster than inter tows.

(a) 3D bidirectional fibrous architecture (b) 3D woven fibrous architecture
Figure 9: Transient flow front tracking on different 3D models at multiscale

The difference between the flow intra and inter tows lead to the generation of bubbles intra and inter tows [16] as presented in figure 10.

Figure 10: Resin flow intra and inter tows under different pressure conditions

The results of the infusion on the fiber reinforcement performs with bidirectional or with woven architecture are compared in figure 11. All infusion is performed on the whole unit cell with same tow volume fractions and the same initial and boundary conditions. The results presented in figure 11 indicates that impregnation on woven architecture will lead to less time than for impregnation on bidirectional structure. This phenomenon can be interpreted as follows: under the same condition of tows fraction, the permeability of complex woven model is higher than bidirectional models.

Figure 11: Infiltration ratio as a function of time

7 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, numerical simulations are based on the geometrical models. Flow front tracking are figured out to compare between different models. The principle permeability variation along the tow waviness route is taken into consideration to achieve a more accurate result. Our significant contribution is that we applied one phase level set method to carry out the transient flow front tracking on 3D models. We note that the variant structures of the fiber unit cell models will have important influence on the impregnation process. All these results offer a better understanding of resin infiltration process on 3D fibrous reinforcement at multi-scale. The appearance of defects such as the formation of voids at meso dual scales can be studied on the basis of these models in further work.

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